

Synthesis of β -Phenethylamines and Related Compounds

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The present communication describes the synthesis of some β -phenethylamines, β -phenylethanolamines and γ -phenylpropanolamines.

β -Phenethylamines are well known for their sympathomimetic action. With a view to study the effects of various substituents such as -Me, -Et, -OMe, and -OEt in different positions of the aromatic nucleus on the physiological activity of β -phenethylamines, the synthesis of a few such amines was carried out and is described here.

In Table I are listed the different β -phenethylamines which were prepared by the reduction of the corresponding β -nitrostyrenes with lithium aluminium hydride as described by Erne and Ramirez¹ in about 60 to 70% yields. The β -nitrostyrenes were prepared by condensing the appropriate aldehydes with nitromethane in glacial acetic acid in the presence of ammonium acetate as reported in literature².

N-Methyl- β -hydroxy-3, 4, 5-triethoxy- β -phenethylamine was synthesised from 3, 4, 5-triethoxybenzoic acid which with cuprous cyanide afforded 3, 4, 5-triethoxybenzoyl cyanide³. Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of the latter yielded β -hydroxy-3, 4, 5-triethoxy- β -phenethylamine which was characterised as its picrolonate. Treatment of the amine with ethyl chloroformate afforded the corresponding carbamate isolated as an oil which was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to N-methyl- β -hydroxy-3, 4, 5-triethoxy- β -phenethylamine, isolated as its picrate.

β -Phenylethanolamines are used in medicine as vasopressors and nasal congestants⁴ and with a view to study the effect of different substituents as well as the lengthening of the chain on the physiological activity, amines of the general formula R-CHOH-CH(R₁)NH₂ were synthesised by the method of Hartung⁵ with some modifications. The starting materials for the synthesis of β -phenylethanolamines were the phenyl ketones which were prepared by a modification of the Friedel-Crafts reaction. It was observed that instead of the acid chloride or the acid anhydride, the acid itself could be used in the reaction in the presence of an excess of anhydrous aluminium chloride⁶. The general procedure consists in refluxing a mixture of 1 mole of the acid, about 3 moles of anhydrous aluminium chloride and an excess of the aromatic component to give yields of the ketones ranging between 66-80%.

The isonitroso derivatives of the phenyl ketones were obtained by reacting them with freshly prepared n-amyl nitrite in the presence of dry hydrogen chloride. The isonitroso derivatives were reduced with Raney Ni or Pd/C to the corresponding aminoalcohols

which were characterised by their hydrochlorides. None of the compounds prepared were found to possess any histamine activity.

As a matter of interest a number of γ -phenylpropanolamines were synthesised. They were obtained from the phenyl ketones by reacting them with formaldehyde and amines (as hydrochloride) under the condition of the Mannich reaction to give the corresponding aminoketones (See Table II). The i.r. spectrum of a typical ketone showed bands at 2768, 2820 (N-alkyl); 1687 (C = O); cm^{-1} . Reduction of the amino ketones with aluminium isopropoxide afforded the corresponding aminoalcohols as colourless oils which failed to yield, any solid derivatives (See Table II). The i.r. spectra of a typical aminoalcohol showed bands at 3396, 3208, 1026 (OH), 2782, 2828 (N-alkyl) cm^{-1} .

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of β -hydroxy-3,4,5-triethoxy- β -phenethylamine: A solution of 3,4,5-triethoxybenzoyl cyanide³ (1 g.) in dry ether was added to a well stirred suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (1 g.) in ether (100 ml.). The reaction mixture was gently refluxed for 6 hr. and then decomposed by adding water (4 ml.) and sodium hydroxide (1 ml., 15% solution, filtered and the ether dried. Removal of ether gave the amine (0.7 g.) as a dark brown oil. Its picrolonate was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 192–94° (Found: N, 13.6. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_5\text{O}_9$: N, 13.2%).

N- [β -Hydroxy- β -(3,4,5-triethoxyphenyl)ethyl] carbamate: To an ice cold solution of the above amine (538 mg.) in water (25 ml.) and chopped ice (4.5 g.) was added ethyl chloroformate (120 mg.) and the mixture shaken vigorously for 15 mins. A solution of sodium hydroxide (100 mg.) in water (2.5 ml.) was added simultaneously with additional ethyl chloroformate (120 mg.) and shaken for 2 hr. at 5–10°. The reaction was extracted successively with ether and chloroform and the combined organic extracts were washed with water and dried. Removal of the solvent gave 320 mg. of a viscous oil which was used as such for further reaction.

N-Methyl- β -hydroxy-3,4,5-triethoxy- β -phenethylamine: A solution of the above carbamate in dry ether was added to a well stirred suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (200 mg.) in dry ether (100 ml.). The reaction mixture was gently refluxed for 70 hr. and decomposed with water (1 ml.) and 15% sodium hydroxide solution (1 ml.). The solution was filtered and the ether dried and removed to give 170 mg. of the amine. Its picrolonate was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 172–74° (Found: C, 54.6; H, 6.1; N, 13.1. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_5\text{O}_9$: C, 54.8; H, 6.0; N, 12.9%).

Preparation of isonitroso-p-chlorobutyrophenone: *p*-Chlorobutyrophenone (18 g.) was dissolved in dry ether (150 ml.) and dry hydrogen chloride was passed through it with mechanical stirring. *n*-Amyl nitrite (25 g.) was added dropwise and the solution warmed. The current of hydrogen chloride and the addition of the nitrite were controlled so that the solvent refluxed gently. After addition of the nitrite was complete, the HCl was passed for 1 hr. and the contents left overnight and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with cold water and shaken with 10% ice cold sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline extract was neutralised by adding it gradually to ice cold hydrochloric acid. The

white crystalline precipitate (12 g.) obtained was washed with water and crystallised from petroleum ether (60–80°), m.p. 62° (Found : N, 6.4. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{11}O_2NCl$: N, 6.6%).

Preparation of isonitroso-p-bromobutyrophenone : It was prepared from *p*-bromobutyrophenone as described above. It crystallised from petroleum ether (60–80°), m.p. 79° (Found : N, 5.8. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{11}O_2NBr$: N, 5.4%).

*Preparation of α -ethyl- β -(*p*-chlorophenyl)- β -ethanolamine* : A solution of iso-nitroso-*p*-chlorobutyrophenone (2 g.) in alcohol (50 ml.) containing Raney nickel (1 ml. of the suspension) was hydrogenated at 40 p.s.i. for 6 hr. The next day, the solution was filtered and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The last traces of alcohol were removed under vacuum. The thick viscous oil was taken up in ether and dry hydrogen chloride was passed through it with cooling. The hydrochloride of the amino alcohol (1.4 g.) was obtained as a white crystalline compound, m.p. 249–50° (Found : N, 6.0. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{15}NOCl_2$: N, 5.7%).

TABLE I

 β -Phenethylamines prepared

β -nitrostyrene	M.P.	Found N%	Calcd. N%	M.P. of picrate of β -phenethylamine.	Analysis Found N%	of Picrate Calcd. N%
1. 4-ethoxy-2,3,6-trimethyl-	97° ^a	6.1	6.3	186–87°	13.0	12.9
2. 3-ethoxy-2,4,6-trimethyl-	semi solid*	—	—	140–42°	12.7	12.9
3. 2-methoxy-3,5,6-trimethyl-	semi solid*	—	—	147–48°	13.6	13.3
4. 2-ethoxy-3,5,6-trimethyl-	paste*	—	—	128–29°	12.5	12.9

* used as such for reduction.

*Preparation of α -ethyl- β -(*p*-bromophenyl)- β -ethanolamine* : It was prepared from iso-nitroso-*p*-bromobutyrophenone as described above. Its hydrochloride had m.p. 260–62° (Found : N, 5.0. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{15}ONClBr$: N, 4.8%).

Preparation of β -ketoamines by the Mannich Reaction : A mixture of the aromatic ketone (8 g.), the amine hydrochloride (5.4 g.) and paraformaldehyde (2 g.) in alcohol (20 ml.) was treated with hydrochloric acid (0.5 ml.) and refluxed for 28 hr. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and water (50 ml.) was added and extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was made alkaline with 40% sodium hydroxide solution and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and dried. Removal of the solvent and distillation of the reddish oils under vacuum yielded the β -ketoamines as colourless oils, which were characterised as their picrates (See Table II).

Preparation of γ -phenylpropanolamines : The β -ketoamine (2 g.) and aluminium isopropoxide (3 g.) were dissolved in dry isopropylalcohol (50 ml.) and refluxed for 4 hr. The solvent was removed by distillation and the last traces under reduced pressure. The residual mass was decomposed with ice and dilute hydrochloric acid, kept overnight, made

TABLE II

No.	β -ketoamine				Yield %	B.P.	M.P. of Picrate	Picrate Analysis		Yield %	B.P.	Analysis			
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄				Found N%	Calcd. N%			Found C%	Calcd. C%	Found H%	Calcd. H%
1	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	39	97-99°/1 mm.	157-58°	13.6	13.33	79	122-24°/1 mm.	74.6	74.61	10.2	9.84
2	Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	32	117-21°/1 mm.	154-56°	12.4	12.32	65	143-47°/1 mm.	63.1	63.3	7.9	7.91
3	Br	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	34	99-101°/1.5 mm.	151-52°	11.5	11.24	—	—	—	—	—	—
4	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	29	121-24°/1.5 mm.	154-55°	12.2	12.5	72	104-108°/1 mm.	76.3	75.98	10.3	10.47
5	H	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	CH ₃	22.6	92-98°/1 mm.	147-48°	13.4	12.96	76	114-16°/0.5 mm.	75.6	75.4	10.5	10.2
6	Cl	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	CH ₃	21	101-104°/1 mm.	155-58°	12.2	11.95	69	127-29°/1 mm.	64.9	64.72	8.4	8.29
7	Br	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	CH ₃	21	89-97°/0.5 mm.	152-54°	11.1	10.92	—	—	—	—	—	—
8	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	CH ₃	32	110-12°/1 mm.	139-44°	11.9	12.12	71	92-98°/1 mm.	76.7	76.59	10.6	10.63
9	H	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	27	118-26°/1 mm.	115-17°	12.6	12.7	63	142-44°/1 mm.	76.2	76.0	10.5	10.41
10	Cl	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	23	134-36°/1 mm.	159-60°	11.9	11.61	66	159-61°/1 mm.	65.7	65.75	8.7	8.61
11	Br	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	30	122-27°/1 mm.	157-58°	10.8	10.62	—	—	—	—	—	—
12	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	24	140-43°/1 mm.	129-31°	12.1	11.8	78	132-34°/1 mm.	77.0	77.1	10.6	10.8
13	H	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	20	130-34°/0.5 mm.	74-76°	12.3	12.12	82	151-53°/1 mm.	76.6	76.59	10.8	10.69
14	Cl	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	21	154-58°/1.5 mm.	140-42°	11.4	11.28	77	169-76°/1 mm.	67.1	66.92	9.1	8.93
15	Br	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	27	120-22°/1 mm.	104-106°	10.3	10.35	—	—	—	—	—	—
16	C ₂ H ₅	23	160-64°/1.5 mm.	93-97°	11.6	11.45	70	137-41°/1 mm.	73.9	73.72	11.2	11.3			

 β -Ketoamines and γ -phenylpropanolamines prepared

alkaline with 40% sodium hydroxide solution and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and dried and the solvent removed. The residual yellow oil was distilled under vacuum to give a colourless oil (See Table II).

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